

**MECHANISMS OF MODERNIZATION OF THE SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT OF
PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGLISH TEACHERS BASED ON
THE APPROACH OF CULTURAL STUDIES IN ORAL SPEECH**

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One mechanism for modernizing the system could be the inclusion of authentic materials in the teaching and learning process. Authentic materials such as movies, television shows, songs, and literature can expose students to different cultural perspectives and provide them with opportunities to explore and analyze different aspects of a particular culture. This can help future English teachers develop a broader understanding of cultural contexts and incorporate them into their own oral communication.

Another mechanism could be the integration of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) into the curriculum. ICC refers to the ability to interact and communicate effectively with people from different cultural backgrounds. By incorporating ICC into the system, future English teachers can develop not only their language skills but also their ability to navigate and understand cultural differences. This can enhance their oral communication skills by allowing them to effectively communicate and engage with diverse audiences.

Furthermore, incorporating technology into the system can also facilitate the modernization of the development of oral speech skills. Technology offers a wide range of resources and tools that can enhance the learning experience and provide opportunities for interactive and collaborative learning. Online platforms, speech recognition software, virtual reality, and multimedia applications can all be utilized to create interactive and engaging learning experiences for future English teachers in the cultural studies approach to oral speech.

Modernizing the system for developing the professional competence of future English teachers using a cultural studies approach in oral speech involves integrating contemporary methods, technologies, and pedagogical strategies while emphasizing the cultural and communicative aspects of language learning. Here are some key mechanisms for achieving this modernization:

1. Integration of Technology : Incorporate modern technology and digital tools into language instruction. This includes using audio-visual materials, online resources, language learning apps, and virtual reality to enhance oral communication skills and cultural understanding.

2. Cultural Immersion: Create opportunities for students to immerse themselves in the target culture. This could involve virtual cultural exchanges, attending cultural events, or participating in language immersion programs.

3. Interdisciplinary Approach : Promote an interdisciplinary approach to language learning. Encourage students to explore cultural studies, anthropology, sociology, and other related fields to gain a deeper understanding of the cultural context in which the language is used.

4. Authentic Materials: Utilize authentic cultural materials such as movies, music, news broadcasts, and literature in the language. These materials provide valuable insights into the culture and help students develop more authentic language skills.

5. Task-Based Learning: Implement task-based language teaching methodologies that require students to complete real-world tasks using the target language. This approach enhances both language proficiency and cultural awareness.

6. Cultural Sensitivity Training: Provide training on cultural sensitivity and intercultural communication. Help future English teachers understand cultural nuances and differences to foster better cross-cultural communication in the classroom.

7. Peer Interaction: Encourage students to interact with native speakers or individuals from the target culture. This can be facilitated through language exchange programs, conversation partners, or virtual exchanges.

Modernizing the system for developing professional competence in future English teachers using a cultural studies approach in oral speech requires a holistic approach that combines language proficiency with cultural awareness, intercultural competence, and the effective use of technology and teaching methods. It should also be adaptable to the evolving needs of both teachers and students in our increasingly interconnected and diverse world.

In conclusion, the modernization of the system for developing the professional competence of future English teachers can be achieved through the integration of the cultural studies approach in oral speech. By incorporating authentic materials, integrating ICC into the curriculum, and utilizing technology, future English teachers can enhance their understanding of cultural contexts and develop their oral communication skills in a more meaningful and effective manner.

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